

Analytical Aspects of Polarography of Alkali Metals in Acetamide Melt*

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Molten acetamide as a non-aqueous solvent for current-voltage relationship of some alkali metals has been studied employing mercury pool, bright PtO, Ag/AgCl and S.C.E. electrodes as reference electrodes. The effect of oxygen and water on the polarographic behaviour of alkali metals have also been studied. The plots of i_d vs. \sqrt{t} and i_d vs. concentration have been obtained and discussed. The plots of $\log i/i_d - i$ vs. E are linear but the values of slopes are different than that required for one electron reversible reduction. The value of the slope of K^+ is lower and that of Li^+ is higher than the theoretical value. These results show the irreversibility of the electrode reaction. Polarographic estimation of K^+ in a few complexes has been reported.

THE behaviour of the alkali metal and alkaline earth metal ions was the subject of Heyrovsky's first polarographic investigation¹. The alkali metal ions are characterised by very negative reduction potentials in the aqueous medium. The choice of supporting electrolytes for determination of alkali metals was necessarily limited and tetraalkyl ammonium halides or hydroxides were only usable salts. Peracchio and Meloche² observed that the alkali metal waves were developed better in a mixture of water and ethanol than in purely aqueous medium. Zlotowski and Kolthoff³ in 50% ethanol and Wawzonek and Runner⁴ in methyl cyanide investigated the reduction for alkali metals. Molten acetamide as a non-aqueous ionizing solvent acts in a pronounced way as a water analogue⁵. Saturated KCl-acetamide is very important as a fused electrolyte in high temperature silver-chloride batteries^{6,7}. It shows a good ability to dissolve many otherwise called insoluble inorganic compounds. Conductometric and potentiometric titrations using a special type of Mo electrode have been carried earlier⁸. Here in this paper now we report a preliminary investigation to the use of acetamide melt at 99-100° as a non-aqueous medium for current-voltage relationship of some alkali metals.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of analytical or reagent grade B.D.H., Pfizer or S. Merck quality.

Polarographic Measurements: D.C. Polarograms were taken with an automatic three electrode Radelkis Hungarian Polarograph OH-102. The capillary having characteristics $m=4.709$ mg/sec. and $t=1.86$ sec. (at 45 cm. of Hg pressure in 0.1M $LiClO_4$ in the open circuit) was used throughout

unless otherwise mentioned. The polarograph was run at a speed of 8 min. for the voltage range of 2 volts at damping 3.

Results and Discussion

(i) *Effect of Electrodes*—The voltage-current curves of acetamide melt using dropping mercury electrode in conjunction with (1) Hg pool, (2) Bright Pt, (3) Ag/AgCl and (4) S.C.E. have been obtained. In the presence of supporting electrolytes the same curves shift towards higher potentials. Some representative curves have been shown in Fig. 1. In case of S.C.E. fluctuations in current recording was observed probably because of junction problem. The polarograms were reproducible after a slight preconditioning on any individual sample. In case of bright Pt electrode a maximum appeared at -0.5 volt. when KSCN was employed as supporting electrolyte. The shape as well as the height of this maximum varied non-linearly with time and concentration of the supporting electrolyte.

(ii) *Effect of Atmospheric Oxygen*—Unlike other non-aqueous solvents contamination by atmospheric oxygen was not a serious problem. At the temperature of melt, i.e., 99-100° the effect of oxygen was negligible as was observed in case of residual current of acetamide. So in the subsequent polarograms the purging of H_2 or N_2 may be avoided. The only precaution kept in consideration was that the acetamide melt remained at that temperature for at least half an hour before recording of polarograms.

(iii) *Effect of Moisture Contamination*—The acetamide was infinitely miscible with water. During the initial investigations necessary precautions were taken to prevent excessive exposure to atmospheric moisture. Since no extreme precautions were taken to exclude contamination from

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FIG. 1

Fig. 1. Voltage-current curves of acetamide melt at DME Curve (1) with Hg pool, (2) with bright Pt and (3) with Hg/AgCl. Curve (1') acetamide + KSCN, (2') Acetamide + KSCN, and (3') Acetamide + KSCN in 0.1M LiClO₄ as supporting electrolyte.

moisture on subsequent polarographic recordings, an investigation was undertaken to discover the effect of water on the half wave potentials and diffusion currents. The results have been recorded in Table 1. There is a noticeable decrease in the

reported polarographic reductions of several cations in various solvents and noticed that as the dielectric constant of the solvent increased there was also a shift in the half wave potentials.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF WATER ON DIFFUSION CURRENT CONSTANT AND HALF WAVE POTENTIAL OF Li⁺

% water	id, μA	corrected concentration mM/liter	$\frac{id}{cm^{2/3}t^{1/6}}$	$-E_{1/2}$ vs. Ag/AgCl volt
0	3.40	1.15	0.9544	0.900
1.25	3.35	1.14	0.9485	0.915
6.25	3.12	1.10	0.9156	0.895
25	2.60	0.98	0.8564	0.886

diffusion current above 25% water. The difference may be due to a more solvated or complexed species resulting from the added water, disrupting the polymer-like chains which are said to exist in acetamide-like solvents⁹. Increasing amount of water indicated no change in half wave potential until after 25% water had been added where there is a noticeable shift to a more positive value. This may be expected since Bruss and De Vries¹⁰ have

(iv) *Effect of Height of Mercury Reservoir*—In presence of 0.1 M LiClO₄ and 0.1 M KSCN by increasing the height id increases and the half wave potential almost remains unchanged under conditions studied. The plots of id vs. \sqrt{h} were linear showing the reduction is diffusion controlled. The value of id/\sqrt{h} was found to be fairly constant. The plots of $\log i/id-i$ vs. E are linear but the values of slopes are different than required for one electron reversible reduction. The value of slope of K⁺ is lower and that of Li⁺ of higher than the theoretical value of 0.0746 at 99°. These results show the irreversibility of the electrode reaction. These results have been summarised in Table 2.

(v) *Effect of Concentration*—By increasing the concentration of K⁺ (taking KSCN) in 0.1M LiClO₄ the diffusion current increases and half wave potential almost remains constant. The id/C comes to a constant value showing that the limiting current is diffusion controlled. The polarographic characteristics have been given in Table 3.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF MERCURY RESERVOIR HEIGHT ON THE POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF ALKALI METAL IONS

Alkali metal salt	Height cm	id μA	$-E_{1/2}$ vs. Hg pool volt	Slope mv	$\frac{id}{\sqrt{h}}$	$\frac{id}{\sqrt{h_{eff}}}$ *
LiCl	25	10.50	0.500	78	2.100	2.164
	35	11.70	0.500	78	1.975	2.021
	45	12.80	0.505	80	1.908	1.940
	55	14.00	0.505	80	1.887	1.916
	65	15.20	0.510	85	1.886	1.917
	75	16.70	0.510	85	1.928	1.948
	85	18.40	0.515	87	1.955	2.013
NaCl	25	9.40	0.270	110	1.880	1.988
	35	10.30	0.270	110	1.739	1.789
	45	11.40	0.272	114	1.609	1.728
	55	12.70	0.270	114	1.712	1.739
	65	13.80	0.275	115	1.712	1.733
	75	15.30	0.275	118	1.766	1.784
	85	16.40	0.277	118	1.779	1.794
KCl	25	8.40	0.287	44	1.680	1.741
	35	9.20	0.287	44	1.554	1.589
	45	10.0	0.290	46	1.491	1.551
	55	10.30	0.290	46	1.388	1.410
	65	11.40	0.290	46	1.415	1.431
	75	12.80	0.295	48	1.478	1.493
	85	14.40	0.295	48	1.562	1.576
RbCl	25	11.40	0.337	91	2.280	2.351
	35	12.90	0.337	91	2.178	2.228
	45	14.10	0.340	93	2.102	2.122
	55	15.60	0.340	93	2.104	2.135
	65	17.70	0.342	99	2.195	2.222
	75	19.80	0.342	94	2.286	2.309
	85	21.75	0.345	95	2.359	2.380
CsCl	25	13.15	0.280	94	2.630	2.712
	35	14.85	0.280	94	2.508	2.566
	45	16.20	0.285	97	2.385	2.455
	55	18.00	0.285	97	2.428	2.464
	65	19.80	0.287	98	2.455	2.485
	75	21.60	0.290	98	2.494	2.520
	85	24.00	0.290	100	2.603	2.626

* $h_{eff} = h - 3.1/m^{1/2}t^{1/2}$ (See I. M. Kolthoff and J. J. Lingane, *Polarography* Vol. 1, p. 78).

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION OF K^+ ON POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS

Conc. of K^+ in 0.1M $LiClO_4$ mM	id μA	$-E_{1/2}$ vs. Ag/AgCl v	Slope mv	$\frac{id}{C}$
1.0	0.678	0.750	87	0.678
5.0	3.390	0.755	90	0.678
10.0	6.810	0.760	88	0.681
15.0	11.2	0.765	85	0.680
30.0	20.4	0.755	99	0.680

TABLE 4—POLAROGRAPHIC ESTIMATION OF K^+ IN SOME COMPLEXES

Complex	Observed conc. mM	Theoretical conc. mM
$K_2Cr(SCN)_6 \cdot 4H_2O$	0.900	0.896
$K_2Cr(C_2O_4)_3 \cdot 3H_2O$	0.985	0.978
$K_2CO(C_2O_4)_3 \cdot 3H_2O$	1.050	1.000
$K_2Al(C_2O_4)_3 \cdot 3H_2O$	1.080	1.072
$K_2Fe(C_2O_4)_3 \cdot 3H_2O$	1.100	1.090

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(vi) *Polarographic Estimation of K^+ in some Complexes*—A calibration curve was drawn taking some known concentrations of KSCN which is sufficiently soluble in acetamide melt.

The polarograms of some unknown complexes containing K^+ were recorded under identical conditions and the values of the diffusion current were referred to the calibration curve for the determination of K^+ in such complexes. Some of the results have been recorded in Table 4.

ANAND : ANALYTICAL ASPECTS OF POLAROGRAPHY OF ALKALI METALS IN ACETAMIDE MELT

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